

Raphitoma zamponorum a new species from São Tome Island (Gastropoda: Raphitomidae)

Raphitoma zamponorum una nueva especie de la isla de Santo Tomé (Gastropoda: Raphitomidae)

Juan HORRO*, Sandro GORI** & Emilio ROLÁN***

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ABSTRACT

This paper describes a new species from São Tome Island of the genus *Raphitoma* Bellardi, 1847 (Mollusca Neogastropoda, Conoidea, Raphitomidae), well known in East Atlantic and Mediterranean Sea. The new species is compared with other similar congeneric ones known in the Eastern Atlantic.

RESUMEN

Este artículo describe una nueva especie de la isla de Santo Tomé del género *Raphitoma* Bellardi, 1847 (Mollusca Neogastropoda, Conoidea, Raphitomidae), bien conocido en aguas del Atlántico Oriental y el Mediterráneo. La nueva especie es comparada con otras congénicas similares del Atlántico Este.

INTRODUCTION

The Raphitomidae Bellardi, 1875 are currently considered a well supported clade of Conoidea (BOUCHET *ET AL.*, 2011). The family is based on the genus *Raphitoma* Bellardi 1847 (Mollusca Neogastropoda, Conoidea, Raphitomidae), a well known genus, but also a very difficult one, with currently fifty-eight Recent species from the Northeast Atlantic and Mediterranean waters accepted as valid (WoRMS, 2018), and an estimated fifty extant species in the Mediterranean Sea alone (GIANNUZZI-SAVELLI, PUSATERI & BARTOLINI (2018).

The genus in the Mediterranean waters is currently under a long revision process by PUSATERI & GIANNUZZI-SAVELLI (2008), PUSATERI *ET AL.* (2012,

2013, 2016, 2017a, 2017b) and GIANNUZZI-SAVELLI, PUSATERI & BARTOLINI (2018), and has also been revised in northern latitudes (HØISÆTER, 2016), but is still not much studied in West African waters. The only paper dealing specifically with this family in this area, is referred to Angola (ROLÁN *ET AL.*, 1998) and was written in a conservative approach, treating as already known species some shells that in posterior papers were considered as different, e.g. *Raphitoma leufroyi* (Michaud, 1828) (see PUSATERI & GIANNUZZI-SAVELLI, 2008) or *Raphitoma purpurea* (Montagu, 1803) (see PUSATERI *ET AL.*, 2017a).

The malacological fauna of São Tomé Island includes a high number of

* Montero Ríos 30-3º, 36201 Vigo, Spain; juanhorro@telefonica.net

** Via Sernesi, 7, 57123, Livorno, Italy; sandrogori53@gmail.com

*** Museo de Historia Natural, Campus Universitario Sur, 15782 Santiago de Compostela, Spain; erolan@emiliorolan.com

endemic species, many of them described along the last twenty-five years, some of them by the authors of this work. This has not been the case with the genus *Raphitoma*. Perhaps it would be no surprise, because the multispiral protoconch present in most Raphitomidae indicates a planktotrophic development which usually origins a wide distribution, and therefore suggests a lower probability of endemism compared to other gastropods.

In the study of saotomean samples (collected mainly by the second author through scuba diving), specimens of *Raphitoma* are rare. We have found only two clearly identified species: *Raphitoma bedoyai* Rolán, Otero-Schmitt & Fernandes, 1998 and *R. corimbensis* Rolán, Otero-Schmitt & Fernandes, 1998.

Together with these, we also found other shells that show apparent differences with the already known ones, specially within the "*R. purpurea* group", but always in limited quantity. Those reasons above mentioned of difficult

species determination, and the usual wide distribution also led us to a conservative approach regarding those *Raphitoma* specimens.

However, in this paper we make an exception and describe a new species because of its unique features. The absence of any similar *Raphitoma* species in European and West African literature makes us absolutely sure of its undescribed condition, even with relatively scanty material and without knowledge of the soft parts.

Abbreviations:

MNHN Muséum National d'Histoire Naturelle, Paris, France.

MHNS Museo de Historia Natural, University of Santiago de Compostela, Spain.

CJH collection of Juan Horro, Vigo, Spain

CPR collection of Peter Ryall, Maria Rain, Austria

CSG collection of Sandro Gori, Livorno, Italy

TAXONOMIC PART

Family RAPHITOMIDAE Bellardi, 1875

Genus *Raphitoma* Bellardi, 1847

Type species: *Pleurotoma hystrix* Cristofori & Jan, 1832 (*nomen nudum*, validated by BELLARDI, 1847 as *Pleurotoma histrix* Jan.) by subsequent designation (MONTEROSATO, 1872: 54).

Raphitoma zamponorum n. sp. (Figs. 1, 2)

Type material: Holotype, Lagoa Azul fundão, West São Tomé, 00°24.49'N-006°36.43'E, 36 m, 8.35 x 3.00 mm (MNHN-IM-2000-33616); paratypes from the same location: n°1, 5.59 x 2.43 mm (CSG), n° 2, 5.63 x 2.38 mm (MHNS); n° 3, 8.21 x 3.22 mm, with broken apex (CJH); n° 4, 6.27 x 2.82 mm (CPR) and n° 5, 5.28 x 2.64 mm (CSG).

Other material examined: Three broken specimens from type location and one more specimen from Minerio Reef at 41 m (all in CSG).

Type locality: Lagoa Azul fundão, West São Tomé.

Etymology: The specific name is after "the zampones", which means people who love to eat, a group of friends with whom the first author has enjoyed many malacological field searches.

Description: Shell of small size for the genus, turreted, with rounded whorls. Protoconch multispiral with 3.5 whorls, height 460-480 μ m, width 400-410 μ m, nucleus 175 μ m, first whorl with cancellate

sculpture, followed by whorls with orthocone axial riblets on the subsutural part and diagonally cancellate sculpture below, the latter occupying more than half whorl. Suture deep, incised. Axial sculp-

Figure 1. *Raphitoma zamponorum* n. sp. Scanning electron micrographs: A: holotype, 8.35 mm (MNHN); B: paratype 1, 5.59 mm (CSG); C: protoconch of the holotype; D-F: microsculpture at different magnifications.

Figura 1. *Raphitoma zamponorum* n. sp. Micrografías electrónicas de barrido. A: holotipo, 8,35 mm (MNHN); B: paratipo 1, 5,59 mm (CSG); C: protoconcha del holotipo; D-F: microescultura a diferentes aumentos.

ture of 9-10 strong ribs with slightly broader interspaces, overrun by prominent spiral cordlets in number of six on the penultimate whorl, the upper one weaker. Spirals are much narrower than their interspaces and also than axial ribs, forming with these a horizontally rectangular cancellation. An extremely fine microsculpture, formed evenly distributed microgranules about 2 μm in size, is present over the entire teleoconch surface.

Columella simple. Outer lip thickened, indented externally by the termination of spiral cords, internally with 7 strong denticles, the two uppermost almost fused and larger. Anal sinus subsutural, U-shaped, moderately deep; subsutural zone with marks of former anal sinus. Siphonal canal wide, siphonal fasciole with 6/7 cordlets, not nodulose.

Shell material semitransparent; background colour light honey with darker honey areas on the subsutural area between axials, many axials pure white and a pure white zone almost forming a band in the middle/lower part of the whorls. Spiral cordlets of the same light honey or white colour, agreeing with the colour of the axials and wall or darker but never white over honey-coloured zones.

Distribution: Only known from the mentioned material from São Tomé Island.

Remarks: As stated above, a multispiral protoconch suggests a planktotrophic larval development and therefore a wide distribution. Therefore, apparent endemism is according to our current knowledge regarding the range of this species, which has not been found as far as we know in any other place, not even in the nearby island of Príncipe. However, taking into account its small size, its habitat not much sampled in most West African places and the usually scarce number of specimens from this genus in all populations, it would not be surprising if it could be found in other locations.

The attribution of this new species to the genus *Raphitoma* seems clear for its conchological characters. Concretely, according to its sculpture of strong axial

costae overrun by prominent, irregularly coloured spiral cords, and from its protoconch features it seems to be involved into "linearis group", being its closer allies *R. linearis* (Montagu, 1803), *R. aequalis* (Jeffreys, 1867) and recently described *R. ephesina* Pusateri, Giannuzzi Savelli & Stahlschmidt, 2017. However it is easy to separate from these related species:

- although *R. linearis* is a very variable species (as shown by HØISÆTER, 2016) there are some constant features different from this new species, particularly the size of the microgranules in sculpture, easily seen in *R. linearis* under high magnification; the higher number of spirals (6 vs 4/5 in the penultimate whorl) and its colour, which in *R. linearis* always includes a completely white ultimate one; the weaker denticles in external lip in that species; and the general colour, which in *R. linearis* includes violet parts, usually in the first whorls.

- *R. aequalis* is easy to separate by its overall aspect, because it has more axial costae, less sculptured, and also a less incised suture, producing a much uniform appearance, and also shows a more regular colour distribution, with light background and coloured spirals except for the last one before suture. It has also a larger protoconch, around 580 μm height, 450 μm width.

- *R. ephesina* is the closest species, in fact young *R. zamponorum* at first sight could be confused. However there are some clear differences such as protoconch size: in *ephesina* according to description, the protoconch is larger, height 520 μm , width 430 μm , it is smaller and specially shorter in *zamponorum* giving it a wider aspect. *Raphitoma zamponorum* is larger with more whorls and a more cylindrical than biconical shape; has less convex whorls with a deeper suture; usually a lesser number of axial costae, which are also less prosocline; has one more spiral cordlet in penultimate whorl; has a deeper anal sinus; has a microsculpture with hard to seen but existing microgranules; and has a lighter colour with more absolutely white parts.

Figure 2. *Raphitoma zamponorum* n. sp. A-C: holotype, 8.35 mm (MNHN); D, E: paratype 1, 5.59 mm (CSG); F, G: paratype 2, 5.63 mm (MHNS); H: detail of the cordlets and sutural parts of the holotype, showing a mark of a former anal sinus; I: anal sinus, specimen from Mineiro Reef, 4.63 mm (CSG).

Figura 2. Raphitoma zamponorum n. sp. A-C: holotipo, 8,35 mm (MNHN); D, E: paratipo 1, 5,59 mm (CSG); F, G: paratipo 2, 5,63 mm (MHNS); H: detalle de los cordones espirales y zona sutural del holotipo, mostrando marca de un anterior sinus anal; I: sinus anal, ejemplar de Mineiro Reef, 4,63 mm (CSG).

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